

HORIZON EUROPE PROGRAMME – TOPIC HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-05

Wind energy in the natural and social environment

Research and Innovation action (RIA)

WIMBY

Wind in My Backyard: Using holistic modelling tools to advance social awareness and engagement on large wind power installations in the EU

Grant Agreement No. 101083460

Starting date: 1st January 2023 – Duration: 36 months

Deliverable D6.4

General Forum objectives, structure and operation

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable number	D6.4
Deliverable title	General Forum objectives, structure and operation
Work Package	WP6
Deliverable type	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Due date	31.10.2023 (Month 10)
Pages	20
Document version	3.0
Lead author(s)	Rebecca Hueting, Deep Blue (DBL)
Contributors	Marta Cecconi, Deep Blue (DBL), Lien Bakelaants, Nazka (NAZKA)

The WIMBY project has received funding from the European Union’s research and innovation programme Horizon Europe under the grant agreement No. 101083460. This document reflects only the author’s view, and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

DOCUMENT CHANGE HISTORY

Version	Date	Author	Description
DRAFT			
0.1	02.10.2023	Rebecca Hueting, Deep Blue (DBL)	Creation
0.2	11.10.2023	Rebecca Hueting, Deep Blue (DBL), Lien Bakelaants, Nazka (NAZKA)	Consolidation of input from contributors
FIRST PEER REVIEW			
1.0	20.10.2023	Luis Ramirez Camargo (UU) Eva Schöll (BOKU), Andrea Hahmann (DTU), Christian Mikovits (BOKU).	Proofreading and peer review
1.1	27.10.2023	Rebecca Hueting, Deep Blue (DBL)	Consolidation of input from reviewers
COORDINATOR APPROVAL			
2.0	31.10.2023	Stella Arapoglou, Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB)	Coordinator review
2.1	31.10.2023	Stella Arapoglou, Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB)	Coordinator approval
FINAL VERSION			
3.0	31.10.2023	Stella Arapoglou, Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB)	Format review, version ready for submission

SHORT ABSTRACT FOR DISSEMINATION PURPOSES

Abstract	This document describes the WIMBY General Forum cross-domain discussion platform linked with the Web-GIS platform. In connection with the web-GIS platform, the General Forum targets local citizens, energy communities, associations and authorities, users' representatives, consumers, policymakers, technology providers, businesses, and industry representatives. The document also reports on its purpose and structure, the co-creation approach and the main roles and responsibilities of Consortium members related to its set-up, operation, and maintenance.
----------	--

LIST OF PARTNERS

No	Logo	Name	Short Name	Country
1		VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	VUB	Belgium
2		DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET	DTU	Denmark
3		INTERNATIONALES INSTITUT FÜR ANGEWANDTE SYSTEMANALYSE	IIASA	Austria
4		UNIVERSITÄT FÜR BODENKULTUR WIEN	BOKU	Austria
5		UNIVERSITETET I OSLO	UiO	Norway
6		NAZKA MAPPS BVBA	NAZKA	Belgium
7		KELSO INSTITUTE EUROPE GEMEINNÜTZIGE GMBH	KIE	Germany
8		DEEP BLUE SRL	DEEP BLUE	Italy
9		UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	UU	Netherlands
10		POLITECNICO DI TORINO	POLITO	Italy
11		UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI PALERMO	UNIPA	Italy
12		APREN-ASSOCIAÇÃO PORTUGUESA DE ENERGIAS RENOVAVEIS	APREN	Portugal
13		MULTICONSULT NORGE AS	MCN	Norway

14		EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZÜRICH	ETH Zürich	Switzerland
15		PAUL SCHERRER INSTITUT	PSI	Switzerland
16		UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON	UCL	United Kingdom

ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
3D	Three dimensional
API	Application Programming Interface
CMS	Content Management System
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIS	Geographic Information System
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience
VPS	Virtual Private Server

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	9
1. Purpose of the General Forum.....	10
1.1 Description	10
1.2 Purpose.....	10
1.3 Basic features.....	11
2. Co-creation approach.....	11
2.1 Set-up and objectives of prototype feedback sessions	11
2.2 Prototype feedback session	12
2.3 Impact-effort exercise	13
2.4 Broad testing and validation.....	13
3. Structure.....	14
4. User registration process.....	15
5. General Forum Data management.....	15
6. Roles, responsibilities, and links with other tasks	15
6.1 Consortium members	15
6.2 Advisory board members	16
6.3 Moderation team.....	16
6.4 Link with the satisfaction analysis and social acceptance framework	18
6.5 Link with the Web-GIS integration	18
6.6 Link with immersive 3D platform.....	18
7. Terms of use.....	19
8. Intellectual Property Rights	19
9. Conclusions and next steps	20

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 - General Forum prototype feedback session.....	12
Figure 2 - Screenshot of the impact-effort matrix exercise	13
Figure 3 - General Forum structure	14

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The WIMBY General Forum, developed by Deep Blue (DBL) under task 6.3, is a cross-domain discussion platform linked with the Web-GIS platform. This deliverable summarises its purpose and structure. The report includes a general description of its main features, the user-centric approach to its development through co-creation and the plan for its set-up and implementation. Moreover, data and privacy management principles are summarised. This deliverable is closely linked to the Web-GIS platform developed by NAZKA under task 5.3 and the immersive 3D platform developed by BOKU under task 5.4. The General Forum definition, set-up and implementation will follow the guidelines defined in D7.3 Data management plan and the strategy defined in D6.1 Communication and dissemination plan.

In section 1 the purpose of the General Forum is described in general terms. In section 2 the co-creation approach adopted to collect requirements and feedback is presented. Section 3 contains the General Forum preliminary structure and in Section 4 a user registration process is proposed. Section 5 defines how data is managed and section 6 specifies how the integration with the WIMBY will happen. Section 6 lists the roles, responsibilities, and links with other tasks and in section 7 reference to standard terms of use is provided. Finally, section 8 identifies the intellectual property rights of contributing partners.

1. Purpose of the General Forum

1.1 Description

The General Forum is a cross-domain discussion platform linked with the Web-GIS platform (T5.3) involving local citizens, energy communities, associations and authorities, users' representatives, consumers, policymakers, technology providers, businesses, and industry representatives. Thanks to the bi-directional nature of online exchanges done through a discussion platform, its objective is to:

- Increase the involvement of impacted communities and stakeholder groups.
- Promote citizens' empowerment providing comprehensive information related to wind-power.
- Increase the efficacy of informed decision making.
- Finally promote knowledge sharing and acceptance.

The core feature of the General Forum is that of allowing users to share comments related to existing, planned, or proposed wind energy farms directly on the Web-GIS map. Published comments can be read and replied to by other users, enabling exchanges and mutual feedback. Comments will be listed and organised in threads. Thematic tags chosen by users will allow searching, filtering and sorting comments, thus facilitating content findability.

1.2 Purpose

The purpose of the General Forum is to ensure that all targeted stakeholders have access to the multiple layers of the WIMBY web-GIS geospatial information and where members' opinions can be exchanged and freely discussed in a multi-stakeholder digital environment. The General Forum platform allows registered users to discuss topics, highlight problems and/or propose solutions related to potential issues arising with existing, planned, or proposed wind-power deployments. Also, discussions can focus on further aspects and impacts not directly related to wind-power which could nevertheless influence opinion building of involved stakeholders and communities. Thanks to cross-exchanges, all users of the platform will have the opportunity to contribute to the research itself.

1.3 Basic features

The General Forum will include the following:

1. Add-to-any or similar plugin, to allow users share contents on social media (only enabled for approved comments).
2. Responsive features, to ensure contents are available and readable both on desktop and mobile devices and compatible with the most used internet browsers (e.g., Chrome, Edge, Firefox, Safari).
3. Customised notifications (e.g., follow thread) and appearance settings for registered users (e.g., dark mode).
4. Adherence to the most recent Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 3 guidelines related to web accessibility^[1], aiming to reach for at least level AA score.

The main language used for its first version will be English, with translation of the main site features in the four pilot sites languages (Norwegian, Italian, Portuguese, German). Comments will not be translated automatically; nevertheless, free online translation services will be recommended during the registration process (e.g., [DeepL](#)²).

2. Co-creation approach

The General Forum will be developed adopting a co-creation approach through which its features and structure are defined collaboratively through interactive activities with partners and external stakeholders in iterative feedback sessions. In this section a description of past, ongoing, and planned sessions is provided.

2.1 Set-up and objectives of prototype feedback sessions

To gather valuable insights and feedback from stakeholders about the function and usability of the discussion forum interface, a prototype feedback session plays a critical role in the design process. It can serve several key purposes like:

1. It ensures that the final product aligns with the preferences, needs and behaviours of the end users.

¹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/> – last visited October 2023

² <https://www.deepl.com/en/translator> – last visited October 2023

2. It helps in validating design decisions by checking whether the design choices align with the user's mental models.
3. It involves users and stakeholders in the design process which increases the sense of ownership and engagement with the product.
4. It gives a structured platform to find out and discuss conflicting opinions about design decisions.
5. It mitigates risk by catching design flaws early in the process which is more cost effective than addressing them during or after development.

2.2 Prototype feedback session

As initial co-creation activity, a basic wireframe prototype of the General Forum has been shared with Consortium members and Advisory Board members in an online meeting on the 6th of October 2023, to collect needs and requirements about the main features to include. Moreover, the user-flow and the high-level usability have been jointly evaluated. This first exercise was structured as an interactive activity on an online Miro board, supporting live interaction with participants while also allowing subsequent and asynchronous feedback over a determined time frame. By doing so the UX/UI design team at DBL was able to determine the essential features of the discussion platform and the users' expectations related to the Web-GIS integration (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 - General Forum prototype feedback session

2.3 Impact-effort exercise

After collecting feedback from the Consortium’s and Advisory Board’s members on the General Forum prototype and its features, a prioritisation exercise will take place. The exercise will focus on the evaluation of the impact and effort required for additional features, until consensus is reached around a defined set of those implementable in the short, medium, and long term. Features that are either not relevant or not feasible will be discarded (see Figure 2).

Figure 2 - Screenshot of the impact-effort matrix exercise

2.4 Broad testing and validation

After the first round of internal testing with Consortium’s and Advisory Board’s members, an advanced prototype will be developed and brought to broad end-users testing through online surveys evaluating its relevance, collecting additional needs and requirements, and testing its usability thanks to Deep Blue’s expertise in User Experience (UX) and User Interface (UI) design. Personas and user-journey maps or similar methodologies might be used for the purpose of making it as user-friendly as possible. To this aim, invitations to testing sessions will be sent to a selection of WIMBY

stakeholders included in the project mailing lists and possibly covering all stakeholder groups identified in task 4.3 and in connection with pilot sites leaders in WP3.

3. Structure

As for the WIMBY website, the online General Forum will be in line with the project’s visual identity and compliant with the most recent General Data Protection Regulation – (EU) 2016/679 and the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG – version 3.0). The General Forum landing page will be linked to the main project website and accessible through the web-GIS platform, as described in task 6.5. From the landing page visitors will be able to access the online community where all discussions are listed (comments and replies organised in threads). Posting, replying, editing, and deleting own comments will be possible only after registration. Signed-in users will also be able to search, filter, sort, and show other users’ published comments on the map. Through the settings area registered users will be able to personalise notification preferences and customise appearance (see Figure 3).

Figure 3 – General Forum structure

4. User registration process

The General Forum will allow:

- Unregistered visitors to read and navigate contents and published comments.
- Signed-up users to navigate all contents and both read and reply to existing comments, as well as adding new ones and editing their own previous comments.

The registration process will require users to sign-up using their email address and choosing a password to access their personal area. Registered users will be able to choose a username which will appear in their comments as author field. Registered users will be able to delete their account anytime and they will have the option to either leave their comments visible or to delete them. Deleting comments will be irreversible and the comments will not be visible anymore online, even though after deletion some comments might have been stored in separate documents by the Consortium partners for research purposes or mentioned in public and internal reports.

5. General Forum Data management

The General Forum platform contents will be hosted on a dedicated virtual private server (VPS) purchased on cloud hosting services recommended for .eu domains and respecting the highest reliability and security standards. It operates through the WordPress content management system or similar content management systems (CMS).

In line with D7.3 Data management plan, the responsible partner Deep Blue and the project coordinator VUB will ensure that data generated by and into the General Forum will be collected and stored in compliance with the most recent GDPR provisions. DBL, as Dissemination Leader, is responsible for the design, realisation, implementation, maintenance, and update of the General Forum over the course of the project and for two years after its conclusion.

6. Roles, responsibilities, and links with other tasks

6.1 Consortium members

All project partners, proportionally with the effort allocated to communication and dissemination activities in WP6 will:

- Promote the growth of General Forum subscribers sharing the related invitations and promotional materials in their networks and through dedicated social media posts.
- Support the definition of key discussion issues in the General Forum area and collecting ideas through workshops, conferences, and literature reviews.
- Engage new and current General Forum's members in supporting the assessment of solutions and exchange of experiences to establish cross-sectoral collaborations and foster the uptake of WIMBY results.
- Initiate, stimulate and engage in discussions with continuity on the General Forum platform.

Partners' contribution will be reported as part of the project Communication and Dissemination activities in task 6.2.

6.2 Advisory board members

The Advisory Board established in task 7.2. will be invited to support the identification and continuous engagement of the General Forum users. This includes but is not limited to i) the promotion of the General Forum during networking events, workshops, and conferences and ii) the circulation of the official invitation to sign-up to the WIMBY platform with all potential stakeholders interested in project results. Also, Advisory Board members will be encouraged to register themselves, publish new comments and reply to existing ones.

6.3 Moderation team

A moderation team will be set-up among Consortium members, to ensure that comments are in line with WIMBY's ethics, with best available practices related to online discussion platforms' moderation, with publication guidelines that will be agreed upon and eventually with GDPR provisions (e.g., publishing information from other sources or individuals without licensing or prior consent). Moreover, dedicated plugins, flagging prompts or similar automated procedures will be implemented to automatically detect and discard inappropriate contents such as "watched words" lists (e.g., violent, offensive, or discriminatory language), "malicious links and

contents detection". The moderation task will consist in ensuring that contents are double-checked by a natural person, with no intervention rights on the opinions expressed or contents included.

The moderation team shall consist of at least one person from each of the six consortium partners most involved in the platform development in WP6 and with the highest total PM allocated to WP6, namely DBL, VUB, BOKU, DTU, UU, NAZKA. All partners will be invited to be part of the moderation team. The moderation team shall be organised in such a way that it ensures new comments and replies are reviewed weekly by at least two Consortium members (e.g., through monthly shifts required once every three months to each moderation team member). In case doubts arise concerning a comment's appropriateness, its content will be brought to the attention of the whole moderation team. When needed, authors will be informed and asked to modify contents. Because of author inaction, contents might be discarded with no further advice. In extreme cases, following the best-known practices in online discussions³⁴, authors might be banned from the platform. Moderation will require limited resources and, if the demand becomes too high over time, all necessary measures will be agreed among partners and adopted to better distribute and allocate the effort. Rules, roles and responsibilities will be better defined by M18 and subject to changes, depending on further developments and partners' internal agreements, as far as the overall resources dedicated to the General Forum are sufficient for its maintenance for the whole duration of the project and two years after its closure. As a final remark, in Deep Blue's experience with similar discussion platforms developed in the context of scientific research, both the risk of inappropriate contents and that of banning users are very low. In all cases, a disclaimer will be included to inform users that views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the WIMBY Consortium nor that of the European Commission and

³ Discourse discussion guidelines <https://meta.discourse.org/faq> - last visit October 2023

⁴ Discourse Terms of Service <https://meta.discourse.org/tos> - last visit October 2023

therefore they are not responsible for any use that may be made of the shared information, nor they can be held responsible for their publication.

6.4 Link with the satisfaction analysis and social acceptance framework

Under WP4 – System analysis, best practice, and trade-offs, a Satisfaction Analysis (SA) framework is being developed and will be used to assess the overall acceptability of wind power plants both at the local level and for the society at large, applying the social acceptance framework at least in the four pilot projects. The General Forum will support those tasks both allowing the analysis of published comments and through the distribution of qualitative and quantitative surveys among registered users.

6.5 Link with the Web-GIS integration

The General Forum discussion platform will be linked to the WIMBY interactive map (Web-GIS) platform through API keys or similar solutions, to allow cross-interaction. More specifically, comments published by users will be related to specific locations or to related wind-energy projects in the nearby area or region. The user-friendly interface will allow users to arrange any new comment on a map, to automatically pinpoint its position on the desired coordinates. Similarly, users will be able to see other users' comments both on the map and in a list view, where also filtering and sorting options will be available. The General forum will help consolidate results of the environmental, technical, economic, and social assessments, thanks to multi-stakeholder interaction.

6.6 Link with immersive 3D platform

As for the web-GIS map, access to a detailed description of the immersive 3D platform will also be possible through a direct link hosted on the main General Forum home page and menu bar. The description will include instructions concerning the hard- and software, practical examples from the pilot regions and pictures from past workshops. Additionally, videos with impressions of the immersive 3D environment can be viewed. This will enable Consortium partners, Advisory Board members and all interested stakeholders to obtain a comprehensive initial assessment of the tool. The integration across these two tools will be further defined during the upcoming months, subordinated to its technical feasibility. To ensure a

smooth integration, DBL team will work closely with the BOKU team as leaders of the task 5.4 related to the immersive 3D platform development.

7. Terms of use

The Terms of use of the WIMBY General Forum will integrate those of the WIMBY Web-GIS, concerning end user registration, personal data collection and terms of use of online services needed to run its essential services.

At their first visit to the Forum, visitors will be asked to give their consent to the privacy and cookie policy, to store essential cookies and, if confirmed, to collect web analytics data. A separate consent will be collected from visitors willing to leave comments on the platform. Contents will undergo moderation activity as shortly described in section 6.3. Comments left by users will be also stored for research purposes for the whole duration of the project and in line with D7.3 - Data management plan.

To use the General Forum and the comment feature, registered users shall give their consent to the treatment of data such as their email address used for registration purposes and the contents produced and published on the platform itself via the comment feature. Registered users will have access to a personal account area where settings, editing options and customisation options will be provided.

The full end-user policy will be coherent with the web-GIS and 3D platform policy provisions and with any other linked tool, agreed with the Coordination team and in compliance with VUB data officer's legal provisions. The full text will be published online on a dedicated web page.

8. Intellectual Property Rights

The General Forum structure, database, code, and interface are developed by Deep Blue and published under the WIMBY project copyrights. The integration of General Forum users' comments on the web-GIS map will be done in collaboration with NAZKA to make them as accessible as possible. The General Forum software and the web hosting and domain are the intellectual property of and are owned by Deep Blue. The structure, database, code and interface of the General Forum and its related software contain valuable trade secrets and confidential information of Deep Blue. In case further input from Consortium members is needed or willingness to contribute to the General Forum development emerges, an exploitation

agreement and the update of IPR provisions might be needed. A complete and updated version of IPR provisions related to the General Forum will be included in D6.5 Exploitation Plan due in M15 (March 2023).

9. Conclusions and next steps

The WIMBY General Forum prototyping is currently underway, in close collaboration with task 5.3 leader NAZKA and task 5.4 leader BOKU. Cross WP5 and WP6 coordination and hands-on meetings are planned to start in November 2023 and will proceed until full alignment will be achieved to ensure a smooth integration across tools.

A first operational version of the General Forum will be made available around M18 (June 2024), in parallel with the first version of the Web-GIS platform and the 3D environment). By then, further end-user testing will be finalised, and main requirements implemented.

Moreover, changes and integrations to the General Forum structure, features and characteristics will still be possible to further align with linked tools and integrate further changes emerging from the testing sessions or needed to keep it up to date.

